

Sample 08a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0013
{Si}	24.2
{Fe}	22.7
{Ca}	13.2
{Si, Ca HiP}	6.7
{Al, Si}	5.5
{S, Ca}	3.2
{Si, Ca LoP}	2.8
{Na, Al, Si}	2.5
{Al, Ca}	2.2
{Al, Si, K}	1.8
{Ca, Fe}	1.5
{Si, Fe}	1.4
{Si, S, Ca}	1.4
{Al, Si, Ca}	1.1
{Mg, Fe}	1.0
{Mg, Ca}	0.9
{Mg, Si}	0.9
{Mg}	0.8
{Mg, Al, Si}	0.6
{Na, Si}	0.4
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.4
{Si, K}	0.3
{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.3
{Zn-LA1}	0.2
{Al}	0.2
{Cl}	0.2
{Na, S}	0.2
{Mg, S, Ca}	0.2
{Al, S, Ca}	0.2
{Na, Si, Cl}	0.1
{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
{S}	0.1
{S, Fe}	0.1
{Na, Si, Ca}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	6.2
Pellet	2.7
Ore preparation undifferentiated	15.2
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	2.2
BOF converter slag	12.2
BOF converter slag slopping	1.3
Slag BOF converter or desulph	2.6
Desulph slag	0.3
Ca-aluminate slag	2.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.5
Olivine flux	0.4
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	3.4
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.2
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.1
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.3
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	4.9
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	3.9
Carbon rich - other	5.7
Cement or BOF converter	1.7
Cement	0.2
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	23.9
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	8.3
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.1
Na-sulphate rich	0.1
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.6

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	24.1
Site - ore / hot metal	2.2
Site - slag	18.4
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	1.9
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	3.4
Site - flux / refractory	0.2
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	0.3
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	4.9
Site - carbon-rich other	3.9
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	5.7
Urban, rarely site - slag	1.7
Urban	0.3
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	23.9
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	8.3
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.2
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/o partial chloride cover)	0.6

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 08b

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0008
	{Si}	38.4
	{Ca}	16.5
	{Fe}	13.7
	{Al, Si}	6.6
	{Si, Ca HIP}	4.3
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.1
	{S, Ca}	1.9
	{Al, Ca}	1.9
	{Al, Si, K}	1.6
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.4
	{Mg, Si}	1.2
	{Si, Fe}	0.9
	{Ca, Fe}	0.9
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.7
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.7
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.7
	{Mg}	0.6
	{Mg, Ca}	0.5
	{Na, Si}	0.5
	{Mg, Fe}	0.5
	{Zn-LA1}	0.4
	{Si, K}	0.3
	{Al}	0.3
	{Zn-LA1, Fe}	0.2
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Cl}	0.2
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.2
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{S}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si, K}	0.1
	{Si, Cl}	0.1
	{Na, Si, S}	0.1
	{Na, S}	0.1
	{Cl}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	3.3
Pellet	1.3
Ore preparation undifferentiated	8.1
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	1.0
BOF converter slag	5.9
BOF converter slag slopping	0.3
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.5
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	1.5
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.8
Olivine flux	0.5
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	7.2
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.1
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.3
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.1
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.9
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	11.0
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	5.1
Carbon rich - other	5.6
Cement or BOF converter	4.5
Cement	0.5
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.1
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	36.3
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	4.2
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.1
Unassigned other	0.7

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	12.8
Site - ore / hot metal	1.0
Site - slag	8.2
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	1.3
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.1
Site - flux / slag	7.2
Site - flux / refractory	0.1
Site - refractory	0.4
Site - scrap	0.9
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	11.0
Site - carbon-rich other	5.1
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	5.6
Urban, rarely site - slag	4.5
Urban	0.6
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	36.3
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	4.2
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.7

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 08c

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0014
	{Si}	57.6
	{Fe}	13.4
	{Ca}	8.5
	{Al, Si}	4.2
	{Si, Ca HIP}	2.5
	{Si, Ca LoP}	1.6
	{Ca, Fe}	1.4
	{Al, Si, K}	1.2
	{Al, Ca}	1.0
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.9
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.9
	{Mg, Ca}	0.9
	{S, Ca}	0.9
	{Si, Fe}	0.7
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.5
	{Mg}	0.4
	{Na, Si}	0.4
	{Al}	0.3
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Mg, Fe}	0.3
	{Mg, Si}	0.3
	{Si, K}	0.2
	{Na, Si, Cl}	0.1
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Zn-LA1}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.1
	{Al, S, Ca}	0.1
	{Cl}	0.1
	{S}	0.1
	{Cl}	0.1
	{Si, Cl}	0.1
	{Na, S}	0.0
	{Al, Si, S, Ca}	0.0
	{Al, Fe}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	3.9
Pellet	0.7
Ore preparation undifferentiated	8.0
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	1.4
BOF converter slag	3.7
BOF converter slag slopping	0.1
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.1
Desulph slag	0.2
Ca-aluminate slag	0.9
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.4
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	3.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.2
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.1
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	5.9
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	4.4
Carbon rich - other	5.2
Cement or BOF converter	1.8
Cement	1.3
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.1
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.3
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.1
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 60 pct	51.2
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	5.3
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.3
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.5

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	12.6
Site - ore / hot metal	1.4
Site - slag	4.9
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	1.4
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	3.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.2
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	5.9
Site - carbon-rich other	4.4
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	5.2
Urban, rarely site - slag	1.8
Urban	1.7
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	51.2
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	5.3
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.3
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.5

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels